

Towards optimal diabetes therapy management: An evaluation of therapy algorithms for type 2 diabetes mellitus at community health centers (CHCs) in Makassar City, South Sula-wesi, Indonesia

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Abstract

The proper use of medications in managing diabetes mellitus (DM) is essential for achieving the best therapeutic results. Assessing the alignment of drug prescriptions with therapeutic algorithms plays a vital role in ensuring effective treatment for DM patients. This study aims to evaluate the appropriateness of medication use in DM patients according to therapeutic algorithms at community health centers (CHCs) in Makassar City, Indonesia. A cross-sectional study was conducted at five CHCs, involving 299 DM patients, including 108 males and 191 females. Data on demographics (gender, age, education, and occupation) and medication use were collected. The rationality of drug use was evaluated based on indication, drug choice, dosage, and patient suitability. Biguanides, especially metformin, were the most frequently used drugs (60.3%), followed by sulfonylureas (29%) and insulin (10.7%). The overall appropriateness of medication use according to therapeutic algorithms was 86%. However, there were shortcomings in terms of correct dosage, where approximately 30.10% of patients still received inappropriate doses. Most DM patients at the studied CHCs received medications aligned with therapeutic guidelines, demonstrating a high level of conformity in prescribing practices.

Keywords

medication suitability, diabetes mellitus, therapeutic algorithms

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disease with a high incidence rate that continues to increase year by year (Cloete 2022). This disease cannot be completely cured

but can only be controlled, thus requiring lifelong therapy, either oral antidiabetic drugs or insulin, with different mechanisms of action in controlling blood glucose levels (Vijan 2015; Reusch and Manson 2017). The choice of antidiabetic therapy is tailored to the needs and clinical

condition of the patient based on the therapy algorithm (Miravet-Jiménez et al. 2020; Padhi et al. 2020). It begins with oral antidiabetic monotherapy, followed by combination antidiabetic therapy and intensive insulin use (Maruthur et al. 2016; Padhi et al. 2020). The inadequate control of diabetes mellitus cases in Indonesia occurs across various healthcare facilities, including primary, secondary, and tertiary care settings (Besemah et al. 2020; Khoiry et al. 2023). According to the National Guidelines for Medical Services for the management of adult type 2 diabetes mellitus, primary care or community health centers (community health center) can initiate insulin therapy (Mathis et al. 2023). This aligns with the Indonesian Medical Doctor Competency Standards, which state that general practitioners are competent to perform comprehensive management to prevent diabetes mellitus complications at skill level 4A (Pradhya et al. 2023). However, in practice, doctors at community health centers (community health center) are only allowed to prescribe oral antidiabetic drugs (OAD) such as metformin, glibenclamide, glipizide, and glimepiride and continue prescriptions from internal medicine specialists under the Referral Back Program (PRB) in accordance with the Indonesian National Formulary (FORNAS), as determined by the Ministry of Health Decree No. 6485 of 2021 (Mathis et al. 2023).

Rational drug use must be appropriate in terms of correct diagnosis, correct indication, correct drug, correct dose, and correct mode of administration. According to WHO, about one-third of patients do not know how to take their medication immediately after leaving the facility, and although half of patients are instructed on how to take their medication, the remaining 80% are often administered by unqualified medical personnel. In addition, 20–50% of drugs are administered without labels, and the dangers of unwarranted drug abuse can negatively affect patients and result in treatment optimization by increasing the cost of care (Feather et al. 2023).

Efforts are made to prevent irrational use of drugs by evaluating drug use. The evaluation stage must be carried out to assess whether the current best evidence used to determine the therapy provided can optimally benefit patients and minimize risks. In this stage, a search can be made for the latest evidence that may have different results from previous treatment decisions. This step is also done to ensure that the intervention that will be given has more benefits than the number of risks incurred (Religioni and Pakulska 2020; Michaelidou et al. 2023). One of the strategies to manage blood glucose levels in diabetic patients is to use medication rationally. Rational medication ensures that patients get safe and cost-effective drugs tailored to their individual clinical needs (Religioni and Pakulska 2020; Michaelidou et al. 2023).

Based on the above background, to achieve treatment targets and prevent the development of the disease into serious complications, drug use evaluation management is needed. Community health center, as one of the front lines of health services for the people of Indonesia, should implement rational drug use according to existing stan-

dards. Inaccurate use of drugs at the community health center level can be detrimental to the wider community. This is because many middle- to lower-class people who make up the majority of the Indonesian population choose health services at community health centers, so it is necessary to evaluate the suitability of the use of antidiabetic drugs in patients at the community health center in the Makassar city area.

Materials and methods

Type of research

The type of research used is the descriptive method. The research was conducted by collecting medical record data of diabetes mellitus patients at five community health centers in Makassar City, Indonesia, including Paccerakang (1), Andalus (2), Cenderawasih (3), Tamalanrea (4), and Jumpandang Baru (5) Community Health Centers.

Population and sampling

The population in this study was all diabetes mellitus patients in 2023 in Makassar City, Indonesia. The sample in this study was diabetes mellitus (DM) patients in five community health centers in 2023. The sample was calculated using the Slovin formula (Alqallaf et al. 2022; Boekoesoe et al. 2023) and obtained a total sample size of 299 samples.

This study used a stratified random sampling method to select participants from various Puskesmas (community health centers) in Makassar City, South Sulawesi Province. This method was chosen to ensure that the sample includes a representative population of all relevant groups in this study, based on certain categories such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, and location of the Puskesmas. With this approach, it is expected that a more varied sample can be obtained and reflect the real conditions in the community so that the research results are more valid and can be generalized to a wider population.

After the health center was selected, participants were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria included patients who had been diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM), were receiving regular diabetes medication therapy, and were willing to participate by providing informed consent. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria included patients suffering from serious comorbidities that affect diabetes management, such as end-stage renal disease, and patients who were unable to communicate or understand verbal or written instructions. Participants were randomly selected from the list of patients who met the inclusion criteria at each selected health center. To ensure representativeness, selection was made based on relevant demographic categories, such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status, so that the sample reflected the diversity of the diabetes patient population in Makassar City.

Several steps were taken to minimize potential bias in participant selection and data collection. Selection bias

was reduced using stratified random sampling, which ensured that each subgroup in the diabetes patient population was proportionally represented in the sample. Measurement bias was reduced by engaging trained researchers who used validated instruments to collect data on medication habits and adherence to therapy, as well as conducting structured interviews and checking the accuracy of medical records. To reduce respondent bias, data on medication adherence and drug use were verified through medical records and interviews with health workers. Finally, to reduce non-response bias, a reminder strategy was implemented to increase participation in the survey by ensuring a sufficiently large number of participants from each health center. With these measures, it is expected to obtain a representative sample and research results that better reflect the real conditions in diabetes management in the community.

Study variables and instruments

This descriptive research focuses on examining the relationship between the use of diabetes mellitus (DM) medication and its alignment with the DM therapy algorithm among patients in Makassar. The independent variable in this study is the use of DM medication, where data will be collected regarding the name of the drug and the dosage prescribed to each patient. Indicators for this variable include the specific medications prescribed for managing diabetes mellitus, the frequency, and the correct dosage as per medical prescriptions. The intervening variable is the DM therapy algorithm, which serves as the standard reference for evaluating the prescribed medication's appropriateness.

The dependent variable is the appropriateness of DM medication use based on the DM therapy algorithm, categorized as either "appropriate" or "inappropriate." This evaluation will be conducted by comparing the patient's medication regimen to the established algorithm. The appropriateness is assessed based on whether the prescribed drug and dosage adhere to the recommended guidelines. Additionally, the study will take into account the socioeconomic conditions of the DM patients in Makassar, which may influence the selection and adherence to prescribed therapies.

Data analysis techniques

In this research, data is analyzed descriptively by collecting medical records of diabetes mellitus patients at the community health center in Makassar City. The analysis process includes the following steps:

1. Suitability categories are presented in percentage (%) form (Cojic et al. 2021; Gallardo-Gómez et al. 2024). The research data is compiled into data collection tables, followed by data processing and percentage calculation using the following formula:

$$\% = \frac{\text{Frequency}}{\text{Total Count}} \times 100$$

2. Frequency refers to variables such as gender, age, medication use, therapy patterns, drug usage compliance based on the algorithm, drug accuracy, and dosage accuracy (Religioni and Pakulska 2020).

The data will be presented in tables that summarize the frequency and percentage of each category, allowing for a clear interpretation of patient characteristics and the appropriateness of diabetes management in relation to the therapeutic algorithm.

Results and discussion

Socioeconomic features of patients

Based on the socio-economic data of diabetes mellitus patients (Table 1), it can be seen that the majority of patients are women with a percentage of 63.88%, while men are only 36.12% of the total 299 patients. This shows that the prevalence of female patients is higher than male. In terms of age, most patients are in the age group of 45–65 years with a percentage of 57.90%, while patients under 45 years old are only 3.68%, and patients over 65 years old reach 36.45%. This condition confirms that diabetes mellitus is more commonly found in the middle-aged to elderly age group.

Table 1. Demographic and socioeconomic profile of the participants.

No	Variables	Frequency Based on Health Center					Percentage	
		1	2	3	4	5		Total N
1	Gender							
	Male	26	21	23	19	19	108	36.12
	Female	30	46	52	41	22	191	63.88
							Total	299
2	Age							
	<45	3	2	3	3	6	17	5.69
	45-65	29	27	47	47	23	173	57.86
	>65	24	38	25	10	12	109	36.45
							Total	299
3	Education							
	Elementary	2	13	12	5	1	33	11.04
	Junior high		11	15	30		56	18.73
	High school	12	26	8	15	22	83	27.76
	Diploma/bachelor's degree	3	17	14	10	18	127	42.47
							Total	299
4	Jobs							
	Self-employed				16	8	24	8.03
	Housewife	8	33	14	32	13	100	33.44
	Laborer		17	3	2	2	24	8.03
	Civil servants	2	6	6	3	10	27	9.03
	Retired civil servant		9	7	7	8	31	10.37
	Do not have a job	43		17			93	
							Total	299

The education level of patients also varied, where the majority of patients had a high school education level (equivalent to high school) at 42.48%. Patients with junior high school and elementary school education accounted for 27.76% and 11.04%, respectively, while patients with

D3/D4/S1 education amounted to 14.05%. This level of education may affect patients' knowledge about their disease and treatment. In terms of occupation, the majority of patients are housewives (IRT) with a percentage of 33.44%, followed by self-employed as much as 24.09%, and patients who do not have a job reach 21.07%. Other groups, such as laborers, civil servants, and retired civil servants, have smaller numbers.

From this picture, it can be concluded that diabetes mellitus patients at the community health center mostly consist of women aged 45–65 years, with a medium level of education (high school), and the majority work as housewives. These factors provide important insights into the population most vulnerable to the disease, as well as the potential challenges faced in terms of access and understanding of disease management.

Distribution of antidiabetic drug use

Based on data on the distribution of the use of diabetes mellitus drugs at the community health center (Table 2, Fig. 1), it can be seen that drugs from the Biguanide group, namely Metformin, are the most widely used drugs, with a total of 231 patients or around 60.31% of all patients. Metformin is known as a first-line drug that is often prescribed for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Sulfonylurea group drugs, such as glimepiride and gliclazide, were also used quite frequently, with 109 patients, or 28.46%, and two patients, or 0.52%, respectively, with a total of 111, or 30%, of patients. This drug serves to increase insulin secretion in diabetics.

Table 2. Distribution of the use of diabetes mellitus drugs at the community health center.

Drug Classes	Type of Medicine	Community Health Center					%	
		1	2	3	4	5		Total N
Biguanide	Metformin	23	59	60	54	35	231	60.31
Sulfonylurea	Glimepiridew	5	13	37	35	19	109	28.46
	Gliclazide	-	1	-	1	-	2	0.52
Rapid-acting Insulin	Insulin Aspart	1	1	2	2	3	9	2.35
α -Glucosidase Inhibitor	Acarbose	-	3	3	-	1	7	1.83
Long-acting Insulin	Insulin Glargine	-	5	6	2	2	15	3.92
	Insulin Detemir	-	-	3	1	-	4	1.04
Premix Insulin	Premix Insulin	1	-	-	4	1	6	1.57
	Degludec+Aspart							

Figure 1. Graph of the distribution of the diabetes mellitus drug's use.

The use of rapid-acting insulin, such as insulin aspart, was recorded in nine patients, or about 2.35%. This type

of insulin is usually used in patients who require rapid blood sugar control. In addition, the drug Acarbose from the Glucosidase Inhibitor class was used by seven patients, or 1.83%, which serves to slow the absorption of carbohydrates and reduce glucose levels after meals.

Long-acting insulin drugs, such as insulin glargine and insulin detemir, were used by 15 patients, or 3.92%, and four patients, or 1.04%, respectively, of the total population, which helps control blood sugar levels stably throughout the day. Meanwhile, premix insulin was used by six patients, or about 1.57%. Premixed insulin is usually used to control blood glucose levels over a long period of time while helping to control blood sugar spikes after meals.

From the data, it can be concluded that Metformin and Glimepiride dominate the management of diabetes mellitus at community health center, while the use of insulin, both rapid-acting and long-acting, is only given to a small proportion of patients, who most likely have more complex diabetic conditions.

Evaluation of diabetes mellitus drug use

Evaluation of the use of antidiabetic drugs is carried out to determine the suitability of antidiabetic drugs given with Perkeni 2021 standards. For the treatment of complications, no evaluation was carried out because the evaluation of conformity with the Perkeni 2021 standard was only aimed at evaluating oral antidiabetics OHO and insulin. In this study, an evaluation of the rationality of antidiabetics was carried out on the right indication, the right drug selection, the right dose, and the right patient.

Based on the evaluation of the use of antidiabetic drugs in patients at five health centers (Fig. 2, Table 3), the results showed a fairly good level of conformity in several aspects of medication rationality. First, in the aspect of appropriate indication. Appropriate indication in the treatment of diabetes mellitus is the accuracy in using antidiabetic drugs according to the doctor's diagnosis in the medical record file based on the examination of HbA1C levels $\geq 6.5\%$ for diabetes and 5.7%–6.4% for pre-diabetes (McCoy et al. 2020; Cojic et al. 2021). Based on the results of the analyzed medical record files, the number of patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus was as many as 87.29% of patients, and they received antidiabetic drugs in accordance with their clinical indications. This shows that most patients have received therapy that is appropriate for their medical condition, although there are still 12.71% of patients whose treatment is not in accordance with the expected indication. This discrepancy may be due to a lack of thorough assessment of clinical conditions or limited therapeutic options at health facilities.

Secondly, for appropriate drug selection, 86.96% of patients received the appropriate type of drug based on the recommended therapy algorithm. This percentage indicates that in terms of drug selection, the majority of patients received the recommended drugs,

Figure 2. Graph of evaluation of rational use of DM drugs to-taled from the studied community health centers based on the parameters of appropriate indication, appropriate medicine, appropriate dose, and appropriate patient.

Table 3. Detailed evaluation of the antidiabetic drug use in patients at community health centers in Makassar City, Indonesia.

No	Appropriateness of Drug Use Algorithm	Community Health Centers					Total	%
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	Appropriate Indication							
	Appropriate	53	44	73	60	31	261	87.29
	Inappropriate	3	23	2	0	10	38	12.70
						Total	299	
2	Appropriate Medicine							
	Appropriate	53	44	73	60	30	260	86.95
	Inappropriate	3	23	2	0	11	39	13.04
						Total	299	
3	Appropriate Dose							
	Appropriate	49	28	42	60	30	209	69.89
	Inappropriate	7	39	33	0	11	90	30.10
						Total	299	
4	Appropriate Patient							
	Appropriate	56	67	75	60	41	299	100
	Inappropriate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
						Total	299	

although there were 13.04% of patients who did not comply with the correct drug choice. Factors affecting this discrepancy could be related to the availability of drugs in health facilities or the presence of certain clinical preferences that are not in accordance with therapeutic guidelines.

Third, in the aspect of correct dosage, the evaluation results showed that only 69.90% of patients received the correct dosage of drugs. This means that around 30.10% of patients did not receive the appropriate dose, which could have an impact on the effectiveness of their glycemic control. This inappropriate dosage needs to be a major concern, as correct dosage adjustment is crucial in optimizing antidiabetic therapy to avoid complications due to hyperglycemia or hypoglycemia.

Lastly, in terms of patient appropriateness, 100% of patients received medication that was appropriate for their individual profile, such as age, gender, and other comorbid conditions. This shows that the administration of medication has taken into consideration the characteristics of each patient, which is an important component in personalized and comprehensive therapy.

The results of this study indicate that there is inaccuracy in dosing in diabetics in several health centers in Makassar City, which is influenced by factors re-

lated to health workers, service systems, and patients themselves. The main factor of dose inaccuracy is the limited knowledge and skills of health workers, which can be overcome by continuing education and the use of digital tools to calculate the dose precisely. Limited consultation time also affects the accuracy of dosing, so increased consultation time and additional health workers are needed.

The findings of our study showed a high level of concordance (86%) in the prescribing of diabetes medications at puskesmas in Makassar, in accordance with therapeutic algorithms. This is in line with previous studies that emphasize the importance of adherence to evidence-based guidelines in improving treatment outcomes of DM patients (Williams et al. 2014). However, the issue of dose discrepancy found in 30.10% of cases underscores a critical gap that needs to be addressed. In line with research in Said et al. 2021, which discusses the role of pharmacists in improving patient safety through better communication of medication guidelines, involvement of health workers, especially pharmacists, in dose optimization and patient counselling.

Patients' lack of understanding of the importance of correct dosage can be addressed with intensive education programs and ongoing counseling (Gudeta and Mechal 2019). In addition, irrational drug use can be minimized by ensuring the availability of drugs in accordance with therapeutic guidelines and conducting regular drug audits. Weak surveillance systems can also be improved by strengthening surveillance and monitoring technology (Gudeta and Mechal 2019).

Social and economic factors also affect patient adherence to therapy, so drug assistance programs and social support should be provided to help patients who have difficulties in purchasing drugs or following therapy (Elwenspoek et al. 2022; Pemberton et al. 2025). The implementation of these interventions is expected to improve dose accuracy and adherence to therapeutic guidelines so that diabetes management at Puskesmas can be optimized (Puspitasari et al. 2022).

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the use of antidiabetic drugs in patients at community health centers in Makassar City, Indonesia, showed sufficient accordance with the guidelines for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Most patients had received drugs that were in accordance with clinical indications (87.29%) and the right type of drug (86.96%) according to the therapy algorithm. In addition, the suitability of drugs with the patient profile has been achieved to the maximum (100%), indicating that drug administration has been adjusted to the individual characteristics of the patient. However, there were shortcomings in terms of correct dosage, where approximately 30.10% of patients still received inappropriate doses. However, this suggests that

dose adjustment should be a major concern in an effort to improve the effectiveness of diabetes mellitus treatment. Overall, although the suitability of drugs and indications is quite good, optimization of therapy, especially in determining the right dose, must be done to achieve better glycemic control and prevent long-term complications in diabetic patients.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

References

- Alqallaf SM, Matar L, Ghuloom K, Alabbad K, Alshaikh F, Alhaddad M (2022) Medication-related burden from the perspective of the elderly. *Medicine and Pharmacy Reports* 95(3): 320–331. <https://doi.org/10.15386/mpr-2133>
- Besemah NA, Sartika RAD, Sauriasari R (2020) Effect of pharmacist intervention on medication adherence and clinical outcomes of type 2 diabetes mellitus outpatients in primary healthcare in Indonesia. *Journal of Research in Pharmacy Practice* 9(4): 186–195. https://doi.org/10.4103/jrpp.JRPP_20_59
- Boekoesoe L, Lalu NAS, Basri KS, Ahmad ZF, Nirmasita A (2023) The knowledge and anxiety toward the implementation of COVID-19 vaccination. *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology & Research* 14(1): 2–5. https://doi.org/10.4103/japtr.japtr_614_22
- Cloete L (2022) Diabetes mellitus: an overview of the types, symptoms, complications and management. *Nursing Standard* 37(1): 61–66. <https://doi.org/10.7748/ns.2021.e11709>
- Cojic M, Kocic R, Klisic A, Kocic G (2021) The effects of vitamin D supplementation on metabolic and oxidative stress markers in patients with type 2 diabetes: A 6-month follow-up randomized controlled study. *Frontiers in Endocrinology* 12: 610893. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2021.610893>
- Feather C, Appelbaum N, Darzi A, Franklin BD (2023) Indication documentation and indication-based prescribing within electronic prescribing systems: a systematic review and narrative synthesis. *BMJ Quality & Safety* 32(6): 357–368. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2022-015452>
- Gallardo-Gómez D, Salazar-Martínez E, Alfonso-Rosa RM, Ramos-Munell J, Del Pozo-Cruz J, Del Pozo Cruz B, Álvarez-Barbosa

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Center for Research and Community Service, Poltekkes Kemenkes Makassar

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study. Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee at Poltekkes Kemenkes Makassar, under approval number 0392/O/KEPK-PTKMS/III/2023. Written informed consent was also obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- F (2024) Optimal dose and type of physical activity to improve glycemic control in people diagnosed with type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Care* 47(2): 295–303. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc23-0800>
- Khoiry QA, Alfian SD, Abdulah R (2023) Sociodemographic and behavioural risk factors associated with low awareness of diabetes mellitus medication in Indonesia: Findings from the Indonesian Family Life Survey (IFLS-5). *Frontiers in Public Health* 11: 1072085. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1072085>
- Maruthur NM, Tseng E, Hutflless S, Wilson LM, Suarez-Cuervo C, Berger Z, Chu Y, Iyoha E, Segal JB, Bolen S (2016) Diabetes medications as monotherapy or metformin-based combination therapy for type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 164(11): 740–751. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M15-2650>
- Mathis A, Spates JD, Suther S (2023) Developing medication therapy management training for community health professionals serving low-income patients. *Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 36(4): 810–816. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08971900221077610>
- McCoy RG, Lipska KJ, Van Houten HK, Shah ND (2020) Association of cumulative multimorbidity, glycemic control, and medication use with hypoglycemia-related emergency department visits and hospitalizations among adults with diabetes. *JAMA Network Open* 3(1): e1919099. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.19099>
- Michaelidou M, Pappachan JM, Jeeyavudeen MS (2023) Management of diabetes: Current concepts. *World Journal of Diabetes* 14(4): 396–411. <https://doi.org/10.4239/wjd.v14.i4.396>

- Miravet-Jiménez S, Pérez-Unanua MP, Alonso-Fernández M, Escobar-Lavado FJ, González-Mohino Loro B, Piera-Carbonell A (2020) Management of type 2 diabetes mellitus in adolescents and young adults in primary care. *Semergen* 46(6): 415–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semerg.2019.11.008>
- Padhi S, Nayak AK, Behera A (2020) Type II diabetes mellitus: a review on recent drug-based therapeutics. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy* 131: 110708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2020.110708>
- Pradhya FP, Sartika RAD, Sauriasari R (2023) “Phardiacare” program for improved medication adherence and clinical outcomes of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients in community health centers. *Current Diabetes Reviews* 19(7): e301122211381. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1573399819666221130104225>
- Religioni U, Pakulska T (2020) Rational drug use in hospital settings - areas that can be changed. *Journal of Medical Economics* 23(10): 1205–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13696998.2020.1801455>
- Reusch JEB, Manson JE (2017) Management of type 2 diabetes in 2017: getting to goal. *JAMA* 317(10): 1015–1016. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.0241>
- Vijan S (2015) In the clinic: Type 2 diabetes. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 162(5): ITC1–ITC16. <https://doi.org/10.7326/AITC201503030>